

Stress Corrosion Cracking of an Impact ModifiedPolyamide and Its Short-Fiber Composites

by

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Abstract

An impact modified Polyamide 6.6 (PA6.6) and two short-fiber composites with different loadings of short glass-fibers were tested under stress-rupture conditions. It was shown that fiber reinforcement can improve the material properties. However its effectiveness depends on fiber orientation. A deteriorating influence on the materials strength, especially at longer times of exposure, can be detected in the aggressive environment of a solution of 5% H₂SO₄ in water. The dependence of the time to final failure on the magnitude of the initial stress intensity factor as well as the rates of crack propagation during loading were measured.

Fatigue testing monitored through an optical microscope resulted in the detection of an increase in critical energy release rate with a decrease in mean load levels.

Introduction

In this study the impact modified Polyamide 6.6 (PA6.6 - trade name nylon 6.6, Zytel ST801) and two of its short fiber composites were analyzed under stress-rupture and fatigue loading conditions [1]. Two different grades reinforced with 17 weight % (9 vol %) short glass-fibers (GF) (a mixture of 50% Zytel ST801 + 50% Zytel 80G33) and 33 weight % (18 vol %) glass fibers (trade name Zytel ST80G33) were also tested.

Stress-rupture Testing

Compact tension (CT) specimens were cut from these plates with the initial notch running either parallel (L-direction) or perpendicular (T-direction) to the Mold Fill Direction (MFD).

Static fracture toughness tests were performed by recording load-displacement curves on an Instron testing machine. The fracture toughness K_C was calculated by using

$$K_C = \frac{F_C}{BW^{1/2}} Y(a/W) \quad (1)$$

where F_C is the maximum load in the loading cycle, B the specimen thickness, W the specimen width and "a" the crack length. $Y(a/W)$ is a correction factor for finite specimen size.

$$Y(a/W) = 29.6(a/W)^{1/2} - 185.5(a/W)^{3/2} + 655.7(a/W)^{5/2} - 1017(a/W)^{7/2} + 638.9(a/W)^{9/2} \quad (2)$$

A more detailed account of the procedure can be found in [2].

Stress rupture tests were performed in air and an acidic solution of 5% H_2SO_4 in water by loading the compact tension specimens with different dead-weights so that different initial stress-intensity factors (K_0) were achieved (Fig. 1). The loading causes a crack to propagate from the machined notch, which in turn leads to an increase in the stress intensity factor at the notch tip and an increase in the rate of crack propagation. The crack propagates in a stable manner until a critical length is reached. At this point, crack length versus time curves were plotted from these data and the crack propagation rates were calculated from these curves.

Fracture Toughness Studies

Figure 2 illustrates the trend in fracture toughness of "super tough modified" Polyamide 6.6 (Zytel ST 801) which occurs when the polymer contains different amounts of short glass fibers. The K_C -values increase

from about $5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ for the neat matrix up to $8.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ for the 18 vol % GF-reinforced composite. For this fiber volume fraction, a clear difference is found between the testing directions, a result, typical for pronounced variations in fiber orientation across the plaque thickness. In case of the lower fiber fraction these differences were not detectable.

The effects dominating stress corrosion cracking of these short-fiber composites are summarized in Figure 3. The matrix strength in air is reduced with a relatively low and constant rate over the entire region, due to crack propagation and creep. The composite undergoes a pronounced decay in strength in the beginning where presumably creeping at the fiber matrix interfaces takes place. An aggressive environment becomes effective only after a certain time of exposure and supports softening of the matrix as well as further reduction in fiber strength.

Theoretical Considerations

The crack growth curves in Figure 4 indicate that the critical stress intensity factor at which the transition to unstable crack growth takes place depends on the loading history. These findings deviate from what is expected in an interpretation of stress corrosion cracking experiments based on LEFM. There the stress intensity factor is assumed to increase, starting from the K_0 -value, until the critical value K_c is reached after some time and the sample fails (Figure 5a). The crack speed is a function of K :

$$\frac{da}{dt} = f(K) \quad (3)$$

The results of the experiments presented here are, at least as far as the matrix is concerned, clearly different as in Figure 5b. Again crack propagation starts at a certain K_0 , but samples tested with different K_0 values do not fail if a definite K_c is reached. Instead, the stress intensity factor at which failure occurs is itself a function of K_0 , most critical values are even higher than the " K_c " derived from a fracture toughness

test. And Equation 3 no longer holds, the crack speed is not a function of K alone but depends heavily on loading history. These results clearly indicate that one can not talk about a critical stress intensity factor as a material constant for the matrix. The limits of LEFM are obviously reached in this case of a very ductile material.

These problems may be attacked using the crack layer theory [3]. This theory does not regard the crack as sharp and localized, but deals with fracture in terms of a damage zone considering the crack as well as any preceding or surrounding damage to be a single thermodynamic entity. All processes in the vicinity of the crack and in the surrounding damaged material are important for the act of crack propagation.

If the problem is restricted to translational damage zone propagation only, the following equation can be derived [4]:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \frac{dD / dt}{\gamma R_1 - J_1} \quad (4)$$

The speed of the crack zone is expressed as the ratio of energy expended on material transformation per time (dD/dt) to the difference between the energy which is required to cause the observed damage (γR_1) and the energy release rate (J_1). The denominator of Equation 4 includes the specific enthalpy of damage γ which is the amount of energy required to cause a single event of damage. R_1 is called the translational resistance moment and is a measure for the amount of damage created in order to propagate the crack by an increment. The product of γ and R_1 hence gives the amount of energy required to propagate the damage zone. J_1 is the energy release rate, i.e., the energy which is set free by the sample during crack propagation.

Application of this equation requires the knowledge of the created amount of damage as well as the measurement of the energy release rate. The resistance moment R_1 is derivable from the amount of damage. It is

defined as the integral of damage density over the trailing edge of the active zone [4]. It is assumed that we have a homogeneous damage density in the damaged regions. That means, that R_1 can be calculated from the increase in the volume of damaged material divided by the increase of the crack surface. The areas of damaged material were determined and are plotted versus the crack length in Figure 6. It is apparent, that the amount of damage gets larger if the initial K_0 is increased. Since the thickness of the samples remains almost constant, it is assumed that R_1 is equal to the slope of the curves in Figure 6, i.e., the increase of the area of damaged material divided by the increase in crack length. The specific enthalpy of damage can be calculated from these data. The denominator in Equation 4 approaches 0 at crack instability, i.e., $\gamma = J_C/R_C \cdot R_C$ is the resistance moment at crack instability, derivable from Figure 6. And J_C is calculated by

$$J_C = \frac{K_C^2}{E} \quad (5)$$

The K_C values were estimated by help of the crack growth curves, i.e., the K-level at crack instability was taken. The data used for these calculations are given in Table 1. Results for γ are included and these are relatively consistent, considering the scatter already present in the input data. These results indicate that there is a quantity which remains invariant of loading history and, thus, can be understood as a local material strength characteristic. At least this is the case for neat materials.

In further experiments under fatigue loading, attempts were made to investigate the influence of loading history on fracture toughness and possibly to introduce the material strength characteristics for the composite.

Fatigue Testing

The materials tested were injection molded tensile bars of Polyamide 6.6 (PA6.6), reinforced with 33 weight % glass fibers (trade name Zytel

70G33L). Several specimens were tested statically to determine the ultimate tensile strength, Young's modulus and to give a starting point for the fatigue tests. A tensile-tensile fatigue regime was employed with a constant minimum/maximum, (R), ratio of 0.2. The mean load levels were varied from 15% to 20% of the ultimate strength thereby inducing differences in the critical release rates.

The relation (5), apparently holds only under the assumptions of LEFM and in the case of a pronounced damage zone it is better to measure the energy release rate directly from the load-displacement curves. This way J_C can be determined experimentally.

Load deflection curves were taken at increasing crack lengths (i. e., 0.25 mm, 0.5 mm, 1.5 mm, ...) until catastrophic failure. These curves were used to calculate incremental energy release rates and, finally, crack growth rate vs. energy release rate curves were plotted to determine J_C .

Each set of load deflection curves is accompanied by a corresponding set of micrographs taken through an optical microscope. The micrographs are of use in later analysis in detecting any differences in the process zone preceding crack growth and differences in Crack Kinetics for tests that were performed at different mean load levels. Further damage analysis has been performed on the fracture surface with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to determine the amount of debonding, fiber pull-out, fiber breakage, etc.

Results

Experimental results show a definite relationship between loading history and J_C . One can see from the graph of da/dN vs. J , Figure 7, that the critical energy release rate increases as the mean load levels are decreased. This is due to the increase in energy, needed to create more damage accumulation at lower mean loads, because of a much longer fatigue life in this case, in comparison to that of the samples tested at the

higher mean load.

Although the above observations indicate that the increase in critical energy release rate should correspond to an increase in the critical amount of damage present when unstable crack growth occurs, only a qualitative difference in damage has been observed. The fracture surface of the samples tested at the higher mean loads show a rougher, more jagged surface indicating a higher degree of brittleness than the samples tested at the lower mean loads.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn

- the composites are superior to the unfilled matrix in resisting crack propagation. The reinforcing effect is most pronounced if the fibers are oriented perpendicular to the crack direction.
- exposure of the material to an acidic environment for times exceeding 10^4 secs considerably decreases the materials strength, especially if glass-fibers are incorporated. This seems to be caused by environmentally induced fiber breakage.
- an influence of loading history on the critical stress intensity level at which the material fails is observable, in particular for the unfilled matrix. The applicability of LEFM seems to be limited in this case of a highly ductile matrix. It seems to be promising to account for the amount of damaged material and to correlate this to the observed toughness.
- the influence of loading history on the critical energy release rate in short glass fiber filled composites, seems to limit the applicability of LEFM to these composites and also indicates that there should be some quantifiable damage present which should be different for samples tested at different loading histories.

References

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- [2] C. Lhymn, J. M. Schultz, J. Mat. Sci. 18 (1983)2923.
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Figure Captions

- Fig. 1: Schematic of the set-up for stress rupture tests.
- Fig. 2: Fracture toughness of composites, derived in static testing, as a function of fiber volume fraction.
- Fig. 3: Schematic diagram of initial stress intensity factor versus time to failure in air and acidic solution. The steep decrease in composite strength at short t_f is attributed to a fiber effect in air, whereas corrosive effects on matrix and fibers can be detected at longer times in acidic solution.
- Fig. 4: Crack growth rates as a function of stress intensity factor with varying K_0 in acidic solution.
- Fig. 5: Schematic representation of the increase in K-level with sub-critical crack growth.
- a): Failure of sample occurs at K_C regardless of what the initial K_0 is
- b): Stress intensity at failure depends on K_0
- Fig. 6: Areas of the damage zones, versus crack length.
- Fig. 7: Crack growth rate as a function of energy release rate for varying mean load levels.
- Table 1: Values used for the evaluation of the specific enthalpy of damage in the ST 801 material.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Table 1

K_o [MPam ^{1/2}]	K_c [MPam ^{1/2}]	J_c [kJ/m ²]	R_c [10^{-3} m]	γ [MJ/m ³]
2.5	5.0	19.2	4.2	4.6
3.2	5.5	23.3	6.4	3.6
4.0	6.0	27.7	6.4	4.3
4.6	7.0	37.7	8.7	4.4

Crack Growth Rate vs Energy Release Rate Fig.7

